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1. Introduction

The Mediterranean is the third richest region in the world in terms of biodiversity, with ca. 25,000 plant species, more than half of which are endemic to the Mediterranean Basin (Strid 1996, Myers *et al.* 2000, Higgins 2009, Poulakakis *et al.* 2014, Sobierajska *et al.* 2016). However, the entire Mediterranean region faces a major problem of habitat loss, habitat degradation and biodiversity loss in general (Mittermeier *et al.* 2004). Human presence and activity over thousands of years have shaped and altered the natural landscape of the Mediterranean region, through deforestation for construction and timber, intensive grazing, fires and infrastructure construction, etc. (Marzo *et al.* 2015). These factors, combined with the climate change crisis, are driving many areas of the Mediterranean to the degradation of their habitats and soils and in some cases even to desertification.

The term “desertification” is used to describe anthropogenic activities and climate processes that cause problems and affect dry areas, such as reduced food production, lack of soil fertility, reduction in the natural resilience of the land and degradation of water quality (UNECED 1992, Xanthopoulos 2010, European Court of Auditors 2018, Pavlidis *et al.* 2018). This phenomenon occurs most often in arid, semi-arid and dry areas with low humidity and can cause poverty, serious health problems due to airborne dust and have demographic and economic consequences, forcing people to migrate from the affected areas (Montanarella 2008).

The Asterousia Mountains are a long mountainous area on the south coast of Crete, in the prefecture of Heraklion (Fig.1). The highest peak is Kofinas with an altitude of 1,231 m. In the interior of the mountain range there are small plateaus that were formerly used as farmland mainly for cereals and also few small vineyards exist.

Figure 1: The area of Asterousia, in the south of Heraklion prefecture. The red line indicate the protected areas of the NATURA 2000 network.

The largest part of the mountain range is included in the protected areas of the Natura2000 network with the codes GR4310013 'Asterousia Mountains (Kofinas)', which is a Special Protection Area (SPA/SPA) for birdlife, as it is home to vultures and other birds of prey, GR4310004 'Western Asterousia (from Agiofarago to Kokkinos Pyrgos)', which is a Special Area of Conservation (SPA/SAC), and GR4310005 'Asterousia (Kofinas)' for the conservation and protection of habitat types, flora and fauna. Soil degradation and desertification are two of the main and long-standing problems in the area and several efforts have been made to reverse these processes and save/maintain the ecosystems. A significant number of endemic and steno-endemic plant species can be found in Asterousia area and it is also home to iconic predator species such as the Gyrfalcon, Vulture, Golden Eagle and Spotted Eagle.

The Restoration Plan for the degraded area of Asterousia is part of the European LIFE project "NewLife4Drylands: Remote Sensing oriented Nature-Based Solutions towards a new life for drylands". The NewLife4Drylands (NL4DL) project aims to help tackle land degradation leading to desertification using Nature-Based Solutions (NBSs). It

aims to provide a framework and protocol for identifying sustainable solutions that could be applied to degraded arid, semi-arid areas, e.g. land restoration activities to improve vegetation cover and productivity in areas where desertification processes are occurring (vulnerable areas). In addition, the project will develop specific techniques for monitoring rehabilitation activities. This project focuses on the development of a Protocol for the identification of dryland characteristics and for the medium and long-term monitoring of restoration interventions of degraded soils, using remote sensing (RS) techniques. The Protocol is based on Earth Observation (EO) Data at high resolution and the application of remote sensing methodologies. In addition, it provides a clear, specific and cost-free assessment of the restoration process, useful for further decision-making in interventions. By combining scientific knowledge, sustainable practices and community engagement, efforts are being made to reverse ecological decline and promote resilience and adaptability to ongoing environmental and climate change. The Restoration Plan proposes Nature-Based Solutions (NBSs) for the restoration and conservation of the Asterousia Mountains area. It is a non-binding roadmap that can be used by stakeholders and local authorities for a collective effort to restore the area to ensure its sustainability for future generations.

1.1. NewLife4Drylands Monitoring Model and Online Tool (NL4DL)

The main objective of the NewLife4Drylands (NL4DL) project is to monitor the implementation, scalability and replicability of Nature-Based Solutions (NBSs) for the regeneration of degraded areas using satellites. Users of satellite imagery will be able to use specific indicators to identify affected areas and corresponding indicators to be able to propose NBSs. This includes the development of a Protocol for NBSs in drylands, including the identification of the characteristics of these areas and the design of NBSs, as well as the supervision of medium and long-term restoration efforts using remote sensing (RS) techniques. This allows for long-term monitoring beyond the usual, typical, short-term solutions in the field. It can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of restoration

activities and to improve sustainable land management. The Monitoring Model (MM) can identify, through remote sensing, potential NBSs using indicators (RS) related to dryland degradation processes to monitor the effectiveness of these Solutions. The MM is designed for users involved in protected area management and planning and it is an advisory tool. Starting from site degradation processes, it can guide users to identify both NBSs and indicators describing conditions and changes in each degradation process to monitor the effectiveness of potential adopted Solutions. The web-based tool is a decision support tool for planners and managers of Protected Areas, accessible via a web link and open to other users (<https://sites.google.com/view/newlifefordrylands/home-page?pli=1>). The indicators (RS) for monitoring land degradation and the information they provide on the soil condition and health are, briefly: (a) Vegetation Indices (NDVI), (b) Burned Area Indices (BAI) or (NBR), (c) Soil Indices (NDSI) or (NDBSI), (d) Soil Salinity Indices (NDSI) and (e) Soil Dryness and Drought Indices (NDDI) or (VCI).

2. Nature-Based Solutions – Proposals for Asterousia Mountains Area

Given the critical situation that the Asterousia Mountains area is facing in relation to the degradation and desertification of many areas of the mountain range, the following Nature-Based Solutions (NBSs) are proposed for the proper utilization and at the same time the protection of ecosystems and the prevention and reduction of soil erosion and degradation with a parallel aim of socio-economic well-being of the region. The proposed NBSs are indicative and not binding and can be used as an advisory and scientific tool for local authorities and government agencies.

2.1. Fencing Areas for Regeneration of Natural Vegetation

The restoration or enhancement of natural vegetation in a particular area involves the installation of fencing to completely exclude or restrict access to people and animals, allowing the land to regenerate and follow the natural ecological succession processes.

2.2. Grazing Management

Banning grazing or implementing intermittent grazing in overgrazed areas such as the Asterousia Mountains are two approaches that can be used on land that has been subjected to excessive or unsustainable grazing respectively. For the specific area, overgrazing is one of the major problems that causes soil degradation and desertification, as the number of grazing animals continues to increase with almost no sustainable management.

Figure 2: Overgrazed area in Asterousia Mountains.

2.3. Crop Management Practices

Agroforestry – micro-gardening: Agroforestry is a sustainable land management system that combines the cultivation of trees or shrubs with crops or animals in a symbiotic way. It is an integrated approach that seeks to optimize the benefits of both agriculture, forestry and livestock. **Crop and livestock production:** Crop rotation is the

successive planting of different crops on the same land in a defined alternating order, helping and promoting the health of soil. **Herbs, aromatic and medicinal plants:** Planting herbs and medicinal plants among olive trees can provide multiple benefits from soil health, soil stability to financial support to farmers' income. **Soil cover:** Applying decaying leaves over freshly sown seeds can help maintain soil moisture, protect seeds from erosion and strong winds, and provide insulation. **Overseeding:** This method involves sowing grass seeds over existing natural vegetation or sparse grass cover to introduce desirable perennial species. This practice is already used in some of the areas, but in such a way that it enhances soil erosion and surface erosion, as farmers tend to tillage the soil against the lines instead following them.

2.4. Soil Management Practices

Application of soil-friendly ploughing practices:

Conservation ploughing tries to reduce the intensity and frequency of ploughing and includes minimum tillage, no-tillage or total tillage systems; **Minimum tillage:** this practice refers to reducing the number and depth of ploughing operations in order not to disturb soil and promote its degradation. **Zero tillage:** Also known as direct seeding, it completely eliminates soil disturbance as no tillage is used. **Strip-tillage:** In this practice, only narrow strips of soil are tilled, usually between the cultivation lines, while leaving the rest of the soil undisturbed. **Contour farming:** Contour farming is a practice where crops are cultivated along the lines and not against them. The latter practice, which is easier and therefore more common, promotes soil degradation and water runoff. The benefits of soil-friendly ploughing practices include reduced soil erosion, improved water retention, enhanced nutrient cycling, increased soil organic matter and improved overall soil structure and health.

Figure 3: Correct and incorrect ploughing. (1) Correct ploughing along the lines. (2) Wrong ploughing against the lines, rainfall will cause erosion and soil retreat.

2.5. Waste Management of Agricultural Products

Composting and landfilling: Organic agricultural waste, such as crop and plant residues and animal manure, can be composted to create nutrient-rich organic matter which will be incorporated in the soil. **Effective irrigation practices:** Proper water management is essential in Mediterranean regions, and in particular in the Asterousia region, to optimize water use and minimize agricultural waste. **Waste reduction:** Promoting waste reduction practices in agricultural crops can minimize the generation of agricultural waste.

Effective management of agricultural waste, especially in degraded areas of the Mediterranean, promotes sustainable land management, enhances soil fertility, reduces environmental pollution and contributes to the overall restoration of degraded land. It is important to integrate these practices into broader land restoration plans and rural

development strategies in Asterousia and also throughout Crete, as the number of agricultural cultivations on the island is quite large.

2.6. Constructions for the Restoration of Degraded Areas

Creation of fences - Windbreaks: When creating fences and/or windbreaks to combat soil erosion and degradation, it is important to consider the specific conditions of the site, such as soil type, slope, prevailing wind direction, and the needs of the local ecosystem. The combination of fences and windbreaks can be an important contribution to soil conservation, water management, improved biodiversity and overall landscape resilience in areas affected by erosion and degradation such as Asterousia.

2.7. Flood and erosion control works

Log fences: Fences are created by placing logs or branches horizontally and vertically to form a barrier. These measures aim to reduce the speed of water flow, trap sediment and stabilize the soil, thus minimizing the risks associated with heavy rainfall and slope instability leading to soil degradation.

2.8. Creation of Drystone Terraces in Areas with High Erosion Problems

The maintenance or creation of new dry stone or/and vegetated terraces in areas with high erosion problems is a land management and conservation practice aimed at preventing soil erosion, stabilizing slopes and preserving the landscape. The technique has been used for centuries in the Mediterranean and in other parts of the world to reverse erosion problems and promote sustainable land use.

Figure 4: Drylands on a small plateau, Mt. Kapsas, Thryпти. (Photo: E. Antaloudaki, Personal archive)

3. Implementation Phase

The implementation phase can be either short or long, depending on the project and the circumstances. During the implementation phase, the management of restoration projects aims to the following:

A. Protection of the site from damage: The restoration works shall not cause further damage to natural resources of the terrestrial or aquatic area affected by the project, including physical damage, chemical pollution or biological pollution (i.e. invasive alien species)

B. Involvement of appropriate participants: Any restoration work should be carried out by or under the supervision of qualified and experienced persons. Wherever possible, stakeholders and local community members shall be invited to participate in the implementation of actions and the use of sustainable materials shall be incorporated into restoration projects.

C. Integration of natural processes: All actions are carried out in a way that responds to natural processes and that promotes and protects the potential for natural and assisted recovery.

D. Responding to changes occurring in the restoration area: Flexible management based on the results of monitoring procedure is applied. This includes both corrective changes to adapt to possible unexpected ecosystem responses and additional work whenever is needed.

E. Compliance Assurance: All projects and works for the restoration fully comply with labour, health and safety legislation. All laws, regulations and permits applicable to the project have to be applied.

F. Communication with stakeholders: All project managers should communicate regularly with key stakeholders for any progress updates and to involve them in the best possible way. Communication should also meet the requirements of the funding bodies.

3.1. Participation of Stakeholders and Local Communities

Desertification is a complex and serious problem that requires long-term commitment and sustained efforts. The Restoration Plan should be implemented with a long-term perspective, with regular monitoring and management program, and with the involvement of local communities and stakeholders throughout the process. Education of local communities and stakeholders on the importance and ways of conservation, proper land management and awareness of the impacts of desertification is very important and essential for the longevity of the project. Thus, involving local communities in decisions on land management, as well as providing incentives for sustainable resource management, is imperative and can help address the underlying social and economic factors that contribute to desertification. It is therefore crucial that local communities are informed before the implementation stage of any project so that stakeholders can help

define the objectives and goals. Moreover, they can contribute potential skills, knowledge, financial and human resources to the development, implementation, maintenance and long-term monitoring. Some common tools and methods for engaging and for a smooth communication and collaboration procedure among all stakeholders include surveys, questionnaires, interviews, workshops, webinars, newsletters and press releases, social media, articles (IUCN 2020).

A successful Restoration Plan for degraded areas requires the active participation, cooperation and empowerment of local communities and organizations. By considering their perspectives and incorporating their knowledge, restoration efforts are more likely to be sustainable and have long-term positive impacts.

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